

Abstract

Diagnosis and Therapy of Fibromyalgia According to Traditional Chinese Medicine: Application of Dr. Guo's Formulas.

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Fibromyalgia is a clinical entity that is difficult to manage within the context of conventional medicine, due to the absence of specific objective markers and the diversity of its clinical manifestations. Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) offers a functional and systemic diagnostic model that can provide relevant contributions to the assessment and treatment of this pathology. This paper aims to describe the diagnosis and therapeutic approach to fibromyalgia according to TCM principles, with a particular focus on the application of herbal formulas developed by Dr. Guo.

According to TCM, fibromyalgia results from energetic imbalances involving *Qi*, Blood, *Yin*, and *Yang*, often associated with Liver *Qi* stagnation, Spleen deficiency, Kidney insufficiency, and the presence of internal Dampness or Wind. Diagnosis is based on a detailed functional assessment, including clinical observation, palpation, pulse and tongue analysis, and the identification of specific syndromic patterns.

The therapeutic intervention prioritises herbal medicine as the central pillar of treatment, through the individualised selection of Dr. Guo's formulas, adapted to European regulatory standards. These formulas aim to regulate the flow of *Qi*, nourish the Blood, eliminate internal pathogenic factors, and restore the body's functional balance. While acupuncture may be used as a complementary therapy, its intensive application can limit its practical viability in cases of chronic fibromyalgia. The clinical experience presented suggests significant improvements in pain levels, sleep quality, emotional balance, and the overall functionality of patients undergoing this personalised approach. Integrating TCM diagnostic principles allows for a therapeutic strategy more closely tailored to individual needs.

This paper highlights the potential of TCM and Dr. Guo's formulas as relevant complementary tools in the multidisciplinary management of fibromyalgia.

Keywords: Fibromyalgia; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Herbal Medicine; Functional Diagnosis; Dr. Guo's Formulas.

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